

ReCcreate

Reusing precast concrete for a circular economy

Stenberg et al.

A digital map of precast concrete systems: background report

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Abstract

The ReCreate project researches the possibilities for deconstructing and reusing precast concrete elements from end-of-life buildings not originally designed for disassembly. The current report describes the study and mapping of existing precast concrete systems of 11 EU-countries with an emphasis on contributing historical and technical knowledge for the reuse of concrete elements. The document is a background report underlying an aggregated European digital map of existing precast concrete systems, which can be accessed here:

[The ReCreate digital map of precast concrete systems](#)

The study has targeted both residential and non-residential precast concrete elements (PCEs), mainly from the post-war period of 1945–1989, through extensive archival research. The information was first organised into country dossiers and then transformed into a map. The aggregated map has been compiled from the data from each country dossier and corresponding maps. It aims to locate both production (factories) and construction (primarily residential mass housing areas) locations of PCEs. The report builds upon the diagrams of the most common PCE, their corresponding building typologies (Hernández Vargas & Stenberg, 2024), and the taxonomy of PCE (Hernández Vargas et al., 2025) as studied in other parts of ReCreate. The work will feed into an element database and support other technical work conducted in ReCreate (Dervishaj & Gudmundsson, 2025; Vullings et al., 2022, 2024).

The archival research has included gathering and analysing vast amounts of primary sources such as drawings, product catalogues, and factory descriptions as well as secondary sources such as articles (scientific, professional, and popular), handbooks, and reports. There is, in general, more research and data available on residential typologies and therefore PCEs of housing systems. The material gathered for this report initiates and adds the research of PCEs of non-residential typologies to the material on housing systems. The country dossiers provide many examples of general and specific details at the system, component, and connector scales, connecting, e.g. to design-related tasks in re-use by providing both a historical narrative and a set of examples or cases to draw experience from.

The map presents the findings country by country. This report also explains how this research can contribute to new tools and methods for estimating the climate impact and environmental savings of PCEs reuse.

The report is organised as follows: Chapter 2 discusses the methodology for data gathering and describes the map and legend. Chapter 3 summarizes the results. Chapter 4 presents a digital tool for the estimation of the precast building stock that was developed during the mapping tasks. Finally, Chapters 5 and 6 include references and appendices supporting the research.

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1. Introduction

Figure 1. Map of the scope for the mapping effort within the project.

This deliverable centres on studying and mapping the typological and geographic distribution of PCEs from the four members of the consortium – Finland (FI), Sweden (SE), Netherlands (NL), and Germany (DE) – and extends with studies and preliminary mappings of seven target countries in Eastern Europe – Estonia (EE), Latvia (LV), Lithuania (LT), Poland (PL), Czech Republic (CZ), Romania (RO), and Bulgaria (BG), as illustrated by Figure 1. In addition, initial or partial mappings have been made of the remaining two target countries Slovakia (SK) and Hungary (HU). Croatia (HR) has not been studied.

The research on the history of precast concrete elements (PCEs) and their applications in Europe is of significant value to scaling up reuse efforts in the construction sector, in addition to its historical significance. This research, therefore, forms part of the wider ReCreate project (Huuhka et al., 2023). A comprehensive study of structural systems and typologies since the advent of precast concrete from multiple countries has been made by gathering source material such as drawings, catalogues, and reports. With the help of this source material, a general map has been constructed to show the country-by-country PCE development (as clickable fields) and a selection of specific locations (as points on the map) Link to the digital map:

<https://josehernandezvargas.github.io/ReCreateMap/>

The study examines the location and make-up of the stock of precast concrete buildings in Europe and addresses the following research question: (1) Where are existing structures built with PCE and their factories, both at the scale of countries and as specific geographic locations, located?

1. 1. Historical context of the expansion of precast construction

PCEs with steel reinforcement for structural frames of buildings were developed in Europe in the late 19th and early 20th century (Elliott & Jolly, 2013). The history of PCEs is still being written and as seen in the study of numerous EU countries in this report, there is less knowledge available of PCEs for non-residential typologies compared to residential typologies even though non-residential PCE were developed earlier.

In the late 1800s and early 1900s, PCEs for non-residential buildings began production to ensure a steady supply of columns, beams, and smaller non-structural elements like stairs, pipes, and blocks. These components supported the construction of factories, offices, and industrial and commercial buildings, facilitating Europe's industrialisation and urbanisation. The easy access to materials for making concrete and the spread of knowledge needed to produce factory-made reinforced concrete helped the technology to establish itself across Europe quickly (Elliott & Jolly, 2013).

After WWII, the massive effort needed to rebuild Europe fuelled the expansion of precast technologies. Since most countries did not have enough people in the building sector to match the demand of new construction, turning towards industrialised processes in general and precast components specifically was also a way to mitigate the rising costs of labour in relationship to materials. PCEs, commonly used in large panel systems for housing, eventually became the defining technology of post-war modernist mass housing projects in Europe (Monclús et al., 2018). Systems of components were developed as a continuation of optimising the use of materials and labour.

In their expansion across the globe, panel systems have traversed national boundaries and linked continents. These global movements were, in some cases, facilitated by the sale of patents for precast systems. In other cases, entire factories were either sold or donated to other nations, stemming from technical missions dispatched to leading countries to acquire expertise, or from the dissemination of technical knowledge by itinerant experts in developing regions. In parallel, such exchanges also arose from economic ventures or from a convergence of economic strategies and political agendas (Alonso et al., 2019). These systems were eventually spread from Europe and then internationally across the globe. The geographical area in the current study, however, is limited to Central, Northern, and Eastern parts of Europe, where vast amounts of PCEs were produced to supply post-war housing.

1. 2. Process and methods

Drawing on the expertise of the four member countries, an initial study was done to assess methods, resources, and availability of archival material. This effort covered Finland, Sweden, the Netherlands and Germany and the findings were recorded in country **dossiers**. The dossiers had an initial structure divided into the four topics: ‘General information’, ‘Bibliography’, ‘Non-residential’, and ‘Residential’, as seen in Figure 2. Digitised (scanned or photographed) material such as catalogues, drawings, and reports from each country was arranged in separate **source material folders** (as seen in Figure 3) with slight variations in structure depending on the type of sources that were available or located in previous research. The dossiers are the analysed and structured results of reading and interpreting the material in the source folders.

Figure 2. The four main topics ‘General information’, ‘Bibliography’, ‘Non-residential’, and ‘Residential’ make up the basic structure of each country dossier. Screen shot of the Estonian Country Dossier General Information page (sourced Feb 20, 2025).

A protocol for data gathering was then established (see Section 2.1) based on the experience of the researchers from the member countries. The purpose of the protocol was to provide a guideline for the data gathering of the target countries. Junior researchers or architects with language skills for each country targeted were then contracted for the equivalent of four to ten weeks of work per target country. During this time, they first studied the general historical distribution of PCE technologies in each target country, then identified where primary sources could be located, visited national archives, and eventually arranged the material and literature in country dossiers. The work was supervised by more senior researchers from member countries, and feedback was given continuously from the ReCreate Work Package 1 team.

Figure 3. Screenshot of the Estonian Source material folder (sourced Feb 20, 2025).

Precast systems and elements are organised according to the classification systems discussed in ‘Building, component, and connector typologies of precast concrete building systems’ (Hernández Vargas & Stenberg, 2024). Identified precast systems are organised in the taxonomic definitions developed in ‘A taxonomy for urban mining of precast concrete’ (Hernández Vargas et al., 2025). Figure 4 shows the main tasks, and their interdependencies used during the mapping.

Figure 4. A diagram with the main steps of the mapping task and their relative interdependencies with other tasks and deliverables within the ReCreate project. Solid lines represent dependencies on other tasks.

1. 3. Scope and limitations of the mapping

The focus of the mapping has been on large precast concrete elements (PCEs), the structural systems of PCEs, and factories for the production of PCEs. Included in the study are precast concrete systems, elements, and connectors of residential and non-residential typologies such as industrial, commercial and institutional buildings. Infrastructure elements, smaller block-sized elements, paving slabs, piping, railway sleepers, posts for exterior use, and bridge elements are excluded.

2. Mapping of concrete elements

2.1. Data-gathering protocol

This section provides an overview of the data-gathering protocol used in the mapping task. The protocol can be found in its entirety as Appendix 6.2. Due to the country-level differences in the amount of previous research and published literature as well as the availability and spread of archival material, there is inevitably significant variance in the strategies used for data gathering by country. In member countries, the data gathering was done by researchers of participating universities, built upon previous research, and enabled visits to a wider selection, and revisits as necessary, of archival institutions because of the longer time span available.

For target countries, mostly master’s level students or recent graduates with relevant language skills were recruited as research assistants and sent for archival fieldwork to collect and digitise source material. The available time frame was usually limited to a maximum of 10 weeks, with approximately one to two weeks spent on fieldwork per country. The time limit necessitated a stricter protocol and prioritisation of visited cities and institutions with the most material available. The protocol was composed based on previous experience from member countries (see Annex 7.2 for more details). Despite the differences by country, the work followed a general outline as illustrated in an exemplary planned timeline for one target country in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Gantt chart of a timeline for mapping one target country. Source: TAU / Niko Kotkavuo.

The first step was identifying relevant national repositories for library and archive catalogues and to look for existing literature such as precast concrete related histories or texts on renovation of existing building stocks to serve as a starting point for the work.

Once starting point literature was acquired, it was used to identify the names of nationally used systems or type series and location-specific terminology to guide further search. Further, by studying historical overviews and reports, the most important or widely used among the systems were identified in order to prioritise the search, and if available, any information on the extent and location of their use and historical origins was collected in the country dossiers.

Once the systems were identified and prioritised, the second phase was to locate source material for each system. Emphasis was on primary sources such as original standards,

catalogues and technical manuals of the systems. Secondary source material, in case primary sources could not be located, were for example industry yearbooks, old trade magazine articles and original construction documentation of identified example buildings.

Once the material had been located, travel plans (in the case of target countries) were made to prepare a schedule for institutions to be visited to make the best use of travelling time. Material was gathered from various institutions that could be identified and accessed, such as university libraries, national archives and municipal archives holding original construction drawings. As a final task after the fieldwork, the found material was organised in a country-level source material folder and then described and processed to help further study by filling in the dossier files for each surveyed country.

2. 2. Map description and legend

The mapping is based on the data on precast elements and systems surveyed in the dossiers. Known instances of precast systems are compiled in a geospatial information system (GIS) organised into countrywide geospatial databases. The map (Figure 6) comprises two main feature types: country-level polygons named **Country information** and point-based layers for buildings and factories referred to as **Building information**. The country polygons represent the member and target countries for which dossiers have been compiled. When a user selects a country, a pop-up displays a summary of the historical development of precast elements and systems. On top of these country polygons, point features mark the areas where buildings using precast elements have been identified. Clicking on these points opens a pop-up displaying the metadata with the information available from the geodatabase, including system codes, year of construction, factory of origin, structural type, number of units, and other relevant descriptors when available. These layers are grouped by country and buildings and can be toggled on and off individually.

Figure 6. Digital map of known instances of precast buildings identified in the Dossiers. Each point represents a geographical area corresponding to a particular structural system. Country polygons display a summary of the data collected in the dossiers.

The information compiled in this geodatabase is structured using the faceted classification developed within the project (Hernández Vargas et al., 2025), where each facet allows situating and drawing parallels across different spatial and historical contexts. Known factories are mapped as point features, specifying at least the following attribute columns:

On top of these country polygons, point features mark the areas where buildings using precast elements have been identified. Clicking on these points opens a pop-up displaying the metadata with the information available from the geodatabase, including system codes, year of construction, factory of origin, structural type, number of units, and other relevant descriptors when available. These layers are grouped by country and buildings and can be toggled on and off individually. Identified buildings are documented at the neighbourhood or city area level, represented by a point feature containing the following attributes:

Table 1. Table of attributes for the geospatial database of buildings.

Column	Data type	Description
country_code	STRING (2)	ISO 3166-1 alpha-2 country code representing the location (e.g., SE for Sweden, DE for Germany).
system_code	STRING (4)	Unique identifier or four-letter code assigned to the precast concrete system type.
system_variation	STRING (4)	Specifies a variation or sub-type of the system, if applicable
factory_code	STRING (4)	Four-letter code representing the factory where the elements were produced.
developer	STRING (4)	Name of the manufacturer or company responsible for producing the precast elements.
structural_type	STRING (4)	Structural load-bearing system classification (e.g., Portal Frame, Wall-Frame, Skeletal System, Cell System). Based on D1.2
building_type	STRING (4)	Functional building typology (e.g., Residential, Industrial, Commercial, Institutional)
location	STRING (255)	Name of the site or area where the precast system/building is located
year	INTEGER	Year of construction
description	STRING	Description of the complex (optional)

Similarly, known factories are mapped as point features, specifying at least the following attribute columns:

Table 2. Table of attributes for the geospatial database of factories.

Column	Data type	Description
Factory code	VARCHAR(4)	Indexed 4-letter alphanumeric unique code
Year (start)	INTEGER	First year of operation
Year (end)	INTEGER	Last year of operation
Description	STRING	Description of the facilities

Most of the data is stored as text (string) data types. The **country_code** field has a fixed length of two characters, while other fields are variable. The year field is stored as a real number (integer) where certain constraints from the literature can be used to prevent typing errors, i.e. only allowing a certain range of valid years for each system.

The geospatial data is displayed on a digital web map using Leaflet (Agafonkin, 2010/2025), an open-source JavaScript mapping library. All geodata is compiled at the country level and then exported as individual files in geoJSON file format, which organises geospatial data into a lightweight, JSON-based format. As a standard open format, geoJSON files can be consumed by external GIS software or web services, supporting further expansion or analysis of the map's results.

Each loaded geoJSON file is automatically assigned to either the **Country information** or the **Building information** group. As the mapping process develops, new findings are appended to the individual layer files, which are loaded asynchronously into the map. This modular structure facilitates straightforward scalability, as new datasets can be added by simply placing them in the data directory and ensuring naming conventions are followed, as illustrated in Figure 7. It also supports robust archival practices. By archiving each geoJSON file individually, the dataset remains maintainable and adaptable for future developments, ensuring that enhancements or revisions can be implemented systematically while maintaining historical records for long-term reference. Additionally, metadata standards, such as ISO 19115 for geospatial data (ISO, 2014), are applied to maintain data integrity and interoperability, ensuring that researchers can retrieve, analyse, and build upon the dataset for further projects.

Figure 7. A pipeline for the data collection and modules for the display of the geospatial database of systems on the web.

3. The digital map

The main result of the mapping task is [The ReCreate digital map of precast concrete systems](#) and its supporting data drawn and compiled from the eleven complete country dossiers and source material folders (both as country descriptions and buildings/points or housing estates/areas). In some cases, the dossiers provide detailed records of precast buildings within entire neighbourhoods (Figure 8). At the European scale, the digital map of this deliverable presents a historical country-by-country overview of the development of precast concrete. The information gathered from the general literature is in some dossiers (for example, Sweden and Germany) aggregated at broader scales such as neighbourhoods, cities, or entire regions. While this aggregated information is valuable for understanding the overall production trends and their historical development, it cannot be directly incorporated into the digital map. The map, therefore, is not comprehensive, and mapped objects (shown as single points) are limited to cases where the geographic location of a selection of buildings or groups of buildings can be clearly identified. In some cases (such as Finland and Poland), overall descriptions constructed from the historical documentation name producers of PCE, regions or cities where the structural systems can be located, but not a specific geographic location. This lack of geographically specific documentation presents a challenge in the mapping effort, and the resolution of specific areas can be improved in future studies.

Figure 8. Example of detailed geographical documentation for the Råslätt neighbourhood in Jönköping, Sweden. Reproduced from (Stalin, 1968).

A forthcoming result will be when the donor PCE of member country pilots are documented by compiling the technical drawings into a BIM format to create a sample database of PCE. This database will also test the potential of and scalability to a larger database. This topic

will be discussed in ReCreate Deliverable 1.4 *Database with Digital Models of Precast Concrete Elements*.

The mapping also recognises the risk and ethical concerns of portraying neighbourhoods of mass housing as mere sources of building materials, especially those with vulnerable social conditions, as pointed out by Jonker-Hoffrén (2023). While the role of PCEs in future reuse provides large environmental benefits when compared with the use of new concrete, these benefits need to be assessed in terms of their social and economic impact. A clear indication of when this risk has turned to reality is when PCEs for reuse are sourced in mass housing areas for the construction of new middle-class housing, as experienced in Denmark with the adoption of the so-called 2018 'Ghetto-law' and the ensuing effort to map the reuse potential of up to 1.3 million square meters of housing as described in the catalogue Ressource Blokken (Heunicke et al., 2021) which does not fully recognize the social effects of sourcing PCE in mass housing areas.

4. Towards a tool for estimation of the building stock

The chapter below is beyond the scope of the present deliverable; however, it is presented as an idea for a next step in mapping of PCE. The tool aims to link a detailed understanding of the *structural systems* of PCE buildings with their *location* in order to provide a more precise estimation of the building stock.

Figure 9. Different mapping scales. Increased resolution allows a more precise estimation of the building stock but depends on the availability of data.

Geospatial databases can efficiently deal with large-scale data management, particularly when handling vast amounts of spatial information on existing building stock. By integrating these databases with BIM models, it becomes possible to enrich spatial datasets with parametric building information, allowing for a comprehensive representation of structures at both macro (territorial) and micro (building elements) levels, as illustrated in Figure 9. For well-known precast systems, the strict modularity of buildings can be used to estimate the overall layout of the building using only cadastral data. This process is based on generating an expected building that fits the overall dimensions of each entry in the geodatabase.

For this, a base geodatabase is filtered and prepared to map historical information to determine a layer of buildings with an identified precast system. GIS data is first used to identify and extract information on existing structures, capturing key geospatial attributes such as building footprints and height. Each of these polygons is then analysed to fit the expected modularity of well-known systems on the filtered polygons, giving an expected number of modules and the overall deviation from the expected measurements. A deviation threshold can be set to filter out poor matches.

Figure 10. Segmentation of the GIS data based on the modular dimensions used in the system. Left: Segmentation algorithm for a single building. Right: Batch-processing of a set of buildings in the same neighbourhood.

Each polygon dimension is then divided by the system’s expected modulation, as shown in Figure 10. A deviation threshold and fitting rules are set up to establish the boundaries of potential matches. Similarly, height information is used to estimate the number of floors in the building. In some cases, the extra height introduced by pitched roofs must be considered. When the number of modules is established, a semantic data structure is exported as input for generating a standardised BIM model. Through parametric modelling, BIM allows for a systematic reconstruction of buildings from technical drawings, ensuring a high level of detail and precision. Figure 11 shows the original documentation used for the modelling and the resulting BIM model, combining the different element types that constitute the precast system. This geospatial dataset is then integrated with attributes calculated from the BIM models, such as a detailed breakdown of structural elements at the component level.

Figure 11. The original construction plans are modelled and compiled into BIM models. Left: Original drawings for the Swedish Skarne 66 precast system. Right: BIM model created according to the historical documentation.

There is however a certain degree of variation within the system. A building may include different internal layouts that involve different amounts and types of elements. While this can be corrected by revising the building documentation for each building, this limits the applicability of this method to larger scales. In this case, the variation is accounted for by incorporating the floorplan variation in the parametric model, which can yield a range of

estimates. This approach has the potential to be expanded to all kinds of precast systems in various countries. However, the scalability of the method depends on collecting sufficient technical information of the precast system at the component level, and a detailed mapping of known instances of existing buildings in the digital map.

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6. Appendix

6.1. Glossaries of PCE terms:

English	Finnish	Swedish	German	Dutch
Apartment	Asunto	Lägenhet	Wohnung	Appartement
Basement	Kellari	Källare	Keller	Kelder
Building section	Lamelli	Segment	Gebäudeteil	Gebouwdeel
Building	Rakennus	Byggnad	Gebäude	Gebouw
Concrete	Betoni	Betong	Beton	Beton
Expansion joint	Laajennussauma	Dilationsfog	Dehnungsfuge	Uitzettingsvoeg
Exterior walls	Ulkoseinä	Exteriörvägg	Außenwände	Buitenmuren
Floor	Lattia	Golv/våning	Boden	Vloer
Ground floor	Pohjakerros	Markplan	Erdgeschoss	Begane grond
Height	Korkeus	Höjd	Höhe	Hoogte
Horizontal	Vaaka	Horisontellt	Horizontal	Horizontaal
Housing estate / Settlements	Asuinalue	Område	Wohnsiedlung	Woonwijk
Insulation	Eristys	Isolering	Isolierung	Isolatie
Interior walls	Sisäseinä	Interiörvägg	Innenwände	Binnenmuren
Joints	Sauma	Fog/möte	Fugen	Voeg
Length	Pituus	Längd	Länge	Lengte
Load-bearing wall	Kantava seinä	Bärande vägg	Tragende Wand	Dragende muur
Module	Moduuli	Modul	Modul	Module
Mortar	Laasti	Bruk	Mörtel	Mortel
Non-load- bearing wall	Ei-kantava seinä	Vägg	Nicht tragende Wand	Niet-dragende muur
Panel	Elementti	Element	Element	Paneel
Partition walls	Väliseinät	Utfackningsvägg / Lättvägg	Trennwände	Scheidingswanden
Polystyrene	Solumuovi	Cellplast	Polystyrol	Polystyreen

Rebar/ Reinforcement	Raudoitus	Armering	Bewehrung	Wapening
Section	Leikkaus	Snitt	Schnitt	Doorsnede
Slab elements	Laattaelementit	Bjälklag	Deckenelemente	Vloerelementen
Staircases	Portaikot	Trappor	Treppenhäuser	Trappenhuisen
Stairs	Portaat	Trappa	Treppe	Trap
Steel (reinforcing)	Teräs (raudoitus)	Stål (armering)	Stahl (Bewehrung)	Staal (wapening)
Upper floor	Yläkerta	Övervåning	Obergeschoss	Bovenverdieping
Vertical	Pysty	Vertikalt	Vertikal	Verticaal
Volume	Tilavuus	Volym	Volumen	Volume
Wall putty	Kitti	Kitt	Wandkitt	Muurplamuur
Weight	Paino	Vikt	Gewicht	Gewicht
Width	Leveys	Bredd	Breite	Breedte

English	Polish	Czech	Bulgarian	Russian
Apartment	Mieszkanie	Byt	Апартамент	Квартира
Basement	Piwnica	Sklep	Мазе	Подвал
Building section	Segment	Tvárnice		Секция здания
Building	Budynek	Stavba	Сграда	Здание
Concrete	Beton	Beton	Бетон	Бетон
Expansion joint	Dylatacja	Dilatace	Дилатация	Деформационный шов
Exterior walls	Ściany zewnętrzne		Външни стени	Внешние стены
Floor	Kondygnacja	Podlaha	Етаж	Этаж
Ground floor	Parter	Přízemí	Партер	Первый этаж
Height	Wysokość	Výška	Височина	Высота
Horizontal	Poziomy	Horizontální/Vodorovný	Хоризонтален	Горизонтальный
Housing estate / Settlements	Osiedle	Sídliště	Жилищен комплекс	Жилой комплекс / Населенные пункты

Insulation	Izolacja	Zateplení	Изоляция	Изоляция
Interior walls	Ściany wewnętrzne		Вътрешни стени	Наружные стены
Joints	Złącza		Съединения	Узлы
Length	Długość	Délka	Дължина	Длина
Load-bearing wall	Ściana nośna	Nosná stěna	Носеща стена	Несущая стена
Module	Moduł	Modul	Модул	Модуль
Mortar	Zaprawa		Мазилка	Раствор
Non-load-bearing wall	Ściana osłonowa	Nenosná stěna	Преградна стена	Ненесущая стена
Panel	Płyta	Panel	Панел	Панель
Partition walls	Ścianki działowe	Příčka	Разделителни стени	Перегородки
Polystyrene	Styropian	Polystyren	Стиропор	Полистирол
Rebar/ Reinforcement	Zbrojenie	Výztuž	Арматура	Арматура/Армирование
Section	Przekrój	Řez	Разрез	Секция
Slab elements	Płyty stropowe		Подов панел	Элементы перекрытия
Staircases	Klatki schodowe	Schodiště	Стълбища	Лестничные марши
Stairs	Schody		Стълби	Лестницы/ступени
Steel (reinforcing)	Piętro		Апартамент	Сталь (арматура)
Upper floor	Wariant		Горен етаж	Верхний этаж
Vertical	Pionowy	Vertikální	Вертикален	Вертикальный
Volume	Objętość	Objem	Обем	Объем
Wall putty	Olkit/kit		Кит	Шпаклевка/щпатлевка для стен
Weight	Masa	Hmotnost	Маса	Масса
Width	Szerokość	Šířka	Широчина	Ширина

6. 2. Data gathering protocol

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Protocol for mapping and data gathering work in WP1

(Revised 241011/ES and based on Finnish experience and Niko Kotkavuos notes from 240520)

Background

The overall goal of gathering the historical and archival material is to make sure that the objectives and deliverables of WP1 can be completed. The four piloting countries (Finland, Sweden, Germany, and the Netherlands) have already been mapped by the country cluster partners. The historical and archival material is collected in dossiers stored in the WP1 folder of the ReCreate Teams channel. In addition, a total of nine target countries have been identified (Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Hungary, Romania, and Bulgaria) of which a minimum of six will be mapped. With support of the partner universities, students or young researchers will do field work to collect the extensive archival material. A general protocol for this data gathering is provided in this document.

WP1 objectives and deliverables

In the ReCreate project application, work package 1 (WP1) has the following objectives (aims):

- to identify, map, order, and analyze precast concrete systems and components used in the EU historically and at present
- to create a taxonomy of system, building, component and connection types
- to create an open database for precast concrete components in the EU

Further, WP1 has four deliverables:

- D1.1 A digital map of existing precast concrete systems (KTH) [M45]
- D1.2 Diagrams of building, component, and connector typologies (KTH) [M36]
- D1.3 A taxonomy for urban mining of precast concrete (KTH) [M45]
- D1.4 A database with digital models of precast concrete elements (KTH) [M36]

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- Installation construction (monteringsbygge in Swedish, montagebauweise in German)
- Panel construction (plattenbau in German)
- [Khrushchevka](#) and [Brezhnevka](#) (former Soviet Union, terms often used for mass housing from Khrushchev era and Brezhnev era, respectively) or [Panelák](#) (in former Czechoslovakia), and etc.
- You can start by using some of the above terminology in a regular Google search or similar and see what comes up (for example, “precast concrete construction systems in Poland”, but in Polish). This may be enough for finding the starting point literature.
- You should also search in library repositories you have been able to identify. It would be best if there is a central repository like Finna in Finland, but in case there isn’t, start with something like a national library (in Finnish case this one holds essentially all books published in Finland that have ISBN number, but the books can only be read at location) followed by university libraries.
- If a specific history book is hard to come by (or perhaps in addition) try scientific repositories like:
 - [Scopus \(Elsevier\)](#)
 - [Web of Science](#)
 - [Academic Search Ultimate \(EBSCO\)](#)
- Universities usually also have guides like [Arkkitehtuuri - Oppaat | Guides at Tampere University Library](#) or [Primo](#) at KTH in Sweden. Look into local university libraries guides, they are likely to have good links and tips.
- Focus on identifying the names of the systems used (or locations of factories) so you can start searching for more specific material on those and hopefully something on the extent of use for each system. Keep in mind we are not looking for only housing (e.g. in Finland BES-system) but other types of construction as well (e.g. in Finland Runko-BES-system). The non-residential construction systems have been written about far less, so they are typically more difficult to find data on.
- Check the bibliographies. With some luck, your starting point literature might already point you to the primary sources for the various systems in their bibliography.

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Preparations for fieldwork

Identifying and locating sources

- List types of sources in approximate order of preference. Keep track of what you will need to see in person using software such as Zotero or similar.
 - Primary sources for systems
 - **Catalogues, technical manuals and standards (very high first priority)**. This is what we hope to find, comprehensive manuals for the various systems with all standardized characteristics that make up the system (measurements, joints, perhaps floorplans etc. depending on the system). In Finnish case, these are found in many university libraries for the most important systems (BES and Runko-BES) and but in other countries you might need to locate them in various archives; like in Sweden where manuals or examples of the 16 largest systems are spread out in numerous national and regional archives,.
 - If original catalogues and technical manual cannot be found or cannot for some reason be reasonably reached, secondary sources can help to make sense of the systems.
 - **Later studies regarding the systems**, for example data on many of the systems used in GDR have been collected into comprehensive catalogues decades after the original use of the systems for construction. This is the **second best thing after the original catalogues and technical manuals** as the “heavy lifting” has already been done.
 - Your starting point literature, which might already include for example some technical drawings or description of the systems as well as other (hopefully scholarly) literary sources.
 - We hope the rest of this list will be unnecessary, as they are far more time and work intensive approaches and **two or three months are not likely to be enough** for good results.
 - Industry year books like Betoniteollisuuden käsikirja (eng. Concrete industry handbook) in the Finnish case and, in the Swedish case Betongvaruindustrin - Katalog över betongvaru- och elementfabriker i Sverige (eng. Concrete Industry – Catalogue over concrete and cement factories in Sweden), which are meant to compile most current and important information for all companies and/or people working within the

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and industry professionals and as such, everything within the pages relates to concrete and much of it also to precast concrete.

- Original building drawings. This is on the fence on whether it should be considered a primary source, as these are the original drawings for the buildings, but as they have likely been drawn according to the original system manuals, I would consider them as secondary sources. These are likely to be stored in a decentralized way in the municipal archives. You would also need to identify particular buildings to study in advance, then place the order at the archive and wait for them to arrive, hoping the arriving material includes something useful. If there is an online service where you can preview the drawings, as there is in some Finnish municipalities, this is a far less risky approach.

Planning for visits

- Once you have identified the sources you will need to see in person, you will need to locate them and plan for library and archive visits.
 - If there are multiple locations where a source is available, try to keep the number of locations to visit to minimum.
 - If a particular source you need is available only in a single location, you will either have to go there or ask if the personnel at the location are willing to scan it for you (likely for a fee).
 - Check for the opening times of the locations you will need to visit (including exceptions during summer).
 - Double check whether the material is available for reading at site, or whether you need to make a request for it beforehand. Take into account the time needed for the material to arrive from remote locations. This is critical for archive visits but often applies to libraries as well.
 - Check if the locations are open to anyone or if you need to apply for a permission beforehand.
 - If permissions are necessary, applying and waiting for permit may take some time so this should be done in good time before visit.
 - Check the policies of each location beforehand.
 - Some may allow for example digital cameras but not mobile phones in their reading rooms.

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- Some may forbid photography altogether but allow taking copies for a fee.
 - Some items may be allowed to be photographed/scanned/photocopied while other may not.
 - Some allow you to have a laptop with you in the reading room, while others may only allow a notebook and pencil.
 - Etc.
- Idea is to have a list of items you will need to see at each location ready before you go and prepare well in order to minimize unpleasant surprises. Special reading rooms in libraries and archives often have limited opening times and the limited time should be spent as efficiently as possible.

Filling in the Dossier

Organization of the dossiers in OneNote

- Each country has a separate dossier (folder) that you can access in the WP1 folder on ReCreate Teams or through this link: [Dossiers](#)
- The starting sub-structure includes tabs for General Information, Bibliography, Non-residential, and Residential. These topics are meant to be filled by selected (and most likely condensed) information that you find as you are searching and data gathering. These pages will contain text, images, and links to original sources. Original sources should be stored in the folder [Source material](#) in the WP1 folder on ReCreate Teams. All “raw material,” gathered i.e. digital photos, PDFs, digitalized manuals, etc should be stored there.
- The page General Information should be a selection of the best overviews of precast concrete elements for the selected country. Select tables, diagrams, etc to help explain what systems were prevalent, which typologies existed, the number and location of factories, and facts and figures regarding the country’s precast building stock. Maps of the geographical spread/location of the precast systems or factories across the country can be added here or on separate pages.
- The Bibliography should list all relevant sources found while data gathering. In the Polish case, the bibliography was simply exported from Zotero.
- The pages dedicated to Non-Residential and Residential building systems should function as headings for a sub-structure of pages where each system receives its own page in OneNote. See, for example, the German dossier where twenty-one residential

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systems are listed, each with a page listing which years the system was in production and a link to a primary source.

- It is ok to add pages in the structure when needed. For example, a list of terminology or glossary translating country specific terms to English may be needed. See for example the Estonian or Polish dossiers.
- Please add any additional country specific material, such as concrete codes in the Finnish dossier or the numbering principles for systems from the Soviet period in the Estonian Dossier, to the dossiers to make them as comprehensive as possible.

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